

Theory of Everything

What is our universe, why is it so beautiful

We know Gravity can bend Space and Time

But for that matter

What is Space, is it what lies in between mass and no mass

We know Black Holes with immense gravity bends Space and Time
more so with its gravity and size and it's Speed

Isn't it beautiful how all the answers are right there

Before we look further let's look closer

What is Gravity

Is it the force of mass existing

We know Gravity exists within our planet and the others as well the
stars

We also know when a Massive Star collapses

It's Mass Collapses, Closer, Denser, Hotter

But it's Gravity ? Increases and so does it's Speed

And For that matter again. What is Gravity. Is it it's Gravitational
forces increasing along with its Speed or is Gravity increasing ?

Can Gravity be a Force / an Energy that constantly wants to

Spin/Accelerate at high rates

But it's Mass holds it's back or rather weighs it down from achieving its free spin

Now Back to our Beautiful Black Holes

We know they bend Space and Time, With greater it's Gravity,
Heavier the Mass, Higher Speeds

Time Bends and Along with it the Space in between everything which is simply just Distance

We Also know Distance can shrink to an observer at certain Speeds but does a Runner say I ran a shorter distance theoretically yes but no

But is it in such cases Truly Shrinking just because speeds increases or as well and Illusion of distance bending

Time seems to stop or slow down immensely when objects / mass entering a Black Hole, not bend ?

And this Shrinking, Bending and Slowing down of time can be explained by our observation of the Black Holes Shape and it's Behaviour

Distance Exists very systematically Inside and Outside a Black Hole

My Theory of an Equation would have to be that

The Time an object would take to enter / nearing a Black Hole = The Time the object would take to traverse the Black Hole's Calculated Distance across Space in a Straight Line at the same Speed

I Believe this can help prove our universe is within a Black Hole and other universes exist in within our own universe and our Black Holes

I Believe Einstein's theory of GR is still beautiful and true to every sense,

This can help bring light to what is a singularity ?

We Know singularities exist within Black Holes, but what if when looked at the right way is just pointing to another Black Hole at the very middle and start of it all,

Because We Also know a Universe too doesn't exist without one in its centre

What is infinity within Gravity And Black Holes, and Our universe ? is it all just simply a single beautiful force/energy that wants to accelerate quicker than anything, to be the fastest

- Navneet Bhurani